

5. Agroforestry Ecoschemes in the New CAP

EURAF Policy Briefing No 5, 22 Feb 2021, Gerry Lawson (policy@euraf.net). 10.5281/zenodo.7953267

EURAF is an NGO, established in Paris on 16/11/2012, with a French Registration number of [W343014937](#) and a Transparency Register ID of [913270437706-82](#). It aims “to promote the adoption of agroforestry practices across Europe by supporting efforts to develop awareness, education, research, policy making and investments which foster the use of trees on farms”. It has a network of 31 affiliated entities in 23 countries.

EURAF welcomes the Commission’s publication on 14/1/2021 of “Agricultural Practices that Eco-schemes could Support” [4], and the [soon to be published Q&A](#). Agroforestry (AF) is one of the ten high level practices listed. This EURAF briefing suggests to Member States how AF could be included within CAP Strategic Plans, and specifically within Eco-schemes. It also clarifies the agroforestry definition in the CAP Rural Development Regulation, and provides a typology for agroforestry practices.

Eco schemes are key to the “green architecture” of the new CAP, and agroforestry is specifically listed in the Farm to Fork Strategy as a good candidate [1]. They are a new Pillar I approach which should “stimulate good farming practices and go beyond enhanced conditionality” [2,3]. Eco-schemes are normally a one-year payment but can be an “entry level scheme” for longer-period Rural Development schemes in Pillar II. They could also fund different annual phases of a larger initiative. They will be mandatory for Member States and optional for farmers. They can be paid either to “incentivise and remunerate” farmers for providing beneficial goods and services or “compensate the cost and income foregone” due to specific practices. Eco-schemes, as described in the draft SP Regulation, should address one or more of the environmental priorities of the CAP:¹

“Groups of trees, Isolated trees, and lines of trees” can be identified by farmers as “Landscape Features” in both the CAP 2014-2020 and the CAP 2021-2027. They can be managed and harvested, but are protected and must be regrown or replaced. They also count towards current “EFAs” and future “non-productive areas” as part of GAEC-9. The Draft Strategic Plan Regulation indicates that Member States should plan for these areas in their Strategic Plans, and should report on them annually (as “Result Indicator 29”).

EURAF recommends consistency in the way that landscape features and silvoarable/silvopastoral areas are recorded by Member States and farmers in national IACS/LPIS systems. Orthophotos, available to all MS, now have pixel resolutions better than 50cm, and it is feasible to have comprehensive and consistent recording of tree and hedge landscape features in place by 2023.

Figure 1 - the contribution that agroforestry and landscape-feature trees (GAEC-9) can make to the countryside. (c) French Agroforestry Association - [agroforesterie.fr](#)

The **existing definition of “agroforestry”** in the Rural Development Regulation (Reg 1305/2013) is robust and flexible: “a land use system in which trees are grown in combination with agriculture on the same land”. However, it should be clarified that the trees can be in the interior of the parcel or on its edges, and that tree

¹ Two further areas were clarified by Parliament - viz “actions to enhance animal welfare or address antimicrobial resistance” - agroforestry has particular value in the context of animal welfare due to the shelter and shade it provides.

Landscape Features are included. Member States *could* further clarify that areas of tree cover which are smaller than their national thresholds for “forest land” (often <0.5ha) can also be considered as agroforestry. This would bring consistency with the UNFCCC rules for national AFOLU/LULUCF GHG reporting.

The EU Biodiversity Strategy anticipates that non-productive areas (GAEC9) should cover as much as 10% of agricultural land...This could have huge benefits in areas where existing tree cover is low (Figure 1), but thresholds would clearly be set at a NUTS2 or NUTS3 level. In Policy Briefing #2 we outlined a method, based on environmental pressures, represented at a 100x100m level, to calculate the territories which have the lowest existing cover of trees outside the forest. Member States could use this methodology to prioritise areas which would receive greater incentives for their Agroforestry Eco-schemes, or to reward farms which already meet the thresholds.

The EURAF agroforestry typology recognises that Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA) in the EU is divided into 3 categories (arable, permanent pasture and permanent crops), and is recorded separately from forest land. Thus, for example we suggest that grazing of forest land should be termed “forest grazing”, whilst on arable lands this would be called “wood pasture”. Forests on farms are clearly not eligible for direct payments - or ecoschemes - but

Tree Location	Agroforestry System	Type of “Land”	
		Agricultural Land	Forest Land
Trees inside parcels	Silvopastoral agroforestry	1 Wood pasture	9 Forest grazing
	Silvoarable agroforestry	2 Tree alley cropping 3 Coppice alley cropping 4 Multi-layer tree-gardens	10 Multi-layer tree gardens
	Permanent crop agroforestry	5 Orchard intercropping, 6 Orchard grazing.	
	Agro-silvo-pasture	7 Alternating cropping and grazing	
Trees between parcels	Tree Landscape Features (protected by CAP Conditionality Rules)	8 Tree-Landscape-Features: (protected hedges, scattered individual trees, trees in line, small groups of trees)	
Trees in settlements	Urban agroforestry	homegardens, allotments, etc.	

they are eligible for Pillar II payments, and MS are strongly encouraged to support forest grazing and transhumance as a means of reducing the risk of forest fires.

EURAF recommends that Agroforestry Eco-schemes can be established anywhere on the UAA of a farm, and that their areas would remain fully eligible for Direct Payments (BISS), providing that the land remains “predominantly” (i.e. more than 50% of ground area) in agricultural production.

EURAF has suggested that five annual Agroforestry Eco-schemes can be offered to farmers. These could be sequential, depending on satisfactory completion of a previous stage:

- **AF1 Planning for trees on farms** - support for consultancy - including soil survey, species advice, and designs for silvoarable/ silvopastoral systems and landscape features.
- **AF2 Landscape-Feature Establishment** - boundary and field-corner planting following the AF Management Plan, particularly on farms with low existing levels of tree-landscape-features.
- **AF3 Landscape-Feature Enrichment** - on farms which already have good coverage of tree landscape features, but which can be widened or extended.
- **AF4 Silvopastoral or Silvoarable Establishment** - multi-year or repeat-year planting of agroforestry in entire parcels or sub-parcels.
- **AF5 Regeneration of Mature Silvopastoral / Silvoarable systems** e.g. parcels of dehesa, parkland, wood pasture.

Areas planted or restored in Agroforestry Eco-Schemes would be marked by farmers on orthophotos in their annual IACS/LPIS returns, and can be verified through the normal “remote sensing spot check” process. Payment levels and ‘regional’ variations need local consultation. Land in all Eco-schemes would remain as agriculture: with full entitlement to Direct Payments and no tree-replanting obligation after felling. **The land would not be classed as “afforestation”**. Payments could focus on regions and districts with low existing cover of silvoarable/silvopastoral systems and landscape features. These Eco-schemes could be considered as “entry requirements” for larger scale Measure 8.2 or AECM schemes in Pillar II - perhaps, administered by Forest Departments.

References

1. European Commission. Farm to Fork Strategy. For a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system. DG SANTE; 2020. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/food/sites/food/files/safety/docs/f2f_action-plan_2020_strategy-info_en.pdf
2. Hart K, Baldock D, Bas-Defossez F, Meredith S, Mottershead D. The eco-scheme proposal for the CAP post 2020: a more effective incentive for environmental enhancement or a largely empty box? European Association of Agricultural Economists; 2019 May. Report No.: 289727. Available: <https://ideas.repec.org/p/ags/eea/172/289727.html>
3. Lampkin N, Stolze M, Meredith S, de Porras M, Haller L, Mészáros D. Using Eco-schemes in the new CAP. IFOAM/IEEP; 2020. Available: <https://www.ifoam-eu.org/sites/default/files/ifoam-eco-schemes-web.pdf>
4. European Commission. List of potential AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES that ECO-SCHEMES could support. DG-AGRI; 2021. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/food-farming-fisheries/key_policies/documents/factsheet-agri-practices-under-ecoscheme_en.pdf
3. Luketić N, Milenov P, Devos W. Management of layers in LPIS: Interaction between LPIS data sets. Joint Research Centre, EU Commission; 2015. Report No.: DS-CDP-2015-10.